

Chat about SOEP Research Data: A RAG System for Interactive SOEP Data Exploration

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December 2025

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17643487>

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Abstract

The German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) is one of the world's longest-running household panel studies, containing rich longitudinal data spanning over four decades. However, the complexity and scale of SOEP data present significant challenges for researchers in data discovery and exploration. This paper presents a prototype Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) system designed to provide conversational access to SOEP research data through natural language queries. Built on OpenWebUI with PostgreSQL and Qdrant vector databases, while leveraging open-weight LLMs, our system enables researchers to interactively explore dataset descriptions, variable definitions, survey questions, and metadata. While currently covering a substantial portion of SOEP datasets, this prototype demonstrates the potential for conversational AI to enhance research data accessibility and streamline the data discovery process for panel data researchers.

Keywords: LLM, AI, RAG, variable search, metadata, DDI

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1 Introduction

The German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) is one of the longest running household panel studies in the world, providing detailed household and individual-level data since 1984. With its comprehensive coverage of socio-economic indicators, demographic characteristics, and behavioral patterns across multiple generations, the SOEP has become an invaluable resource for researchers worldwide (SOEP 2024, Goebel et al. 2019). However, this richness comes with complexity, the dataset encompasses tens of thousands of variables across multiple waves, numerous subsamples, and intricate data structures that can overwhelm both new and experienced researchers (Wagner et al. 2007).

Currently, SOEP data exploration relies heavily on traditional (but already heavily metadata based) documentation, codebooks, and manual navigation through data catalogs, mainly on paneldata.org and companion.soep.de. While comprehensive, these methods often create barriers to easy data discovery, especially among researchers unfamiliar with domain-specific terminology or unfamiliar with the SOEP dataset's structure. The difficulty in understanding variable naming conventions, dataset relationships, and survey methodology can significantly impede the research process.

Advances in Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) systems and conversational AI present new opportunities to transform how researchers interact with complex datasets (Karpukhin et al. 2020, Gao et al. 2023). RAG systems have demonstrated remarkable effectiveness in mitigating hallucinations and enhancing the factuality of large language models by grounding responses in retrieved external knowledge (Assai et al. 2023, Shuster et al. 2021). By combining the power of large language models with structured knowledge retrieval, RAG systems can provide intuitive, natural language interfaces to research data, potentially reducing the time and expertise required for data exploration.

This paper presents a prototype RAG-based conversational interface specifically designed for SOEP data exploration. It aims to provide researchers with an interactive tool for discovering relevant datasets, variables, and methodology information through natural language queries. Our system leverages OpenWebUI (<https://github.com/open-webui/open-webui>) for the chat interface, PostgreSQL (<https://postgresql.org>) and Qdrant (<https://qdrant.tech>) for data storage and retrieval, Pydantic AI (<https://ai.pydantic.dev/>) for the agent framework, and open-weight local language models, with Ollama (<https://Ollama.com/>) serving as the framework for running them.

While this prototype represents a significant step forward in research data accessibility, it is important to note that the system is, as of December 2025, incomplete. Not all SOEP datasets have been integrated, so comprehensive coverage of SOEP remains a work in progress. Additionally, the RAG pipeline is still under development, with key components yet to be implemented. Nevertheless, the existing implementation demonstrates the feasibility and potential impact of conversational AI for research data discovery.

The primary contributions of this work include: (1) the design and implementation of a specialized RAG system for SOEP data exploration, (2) a technical architecture that balances performance with privacy through local model deployment, and (3) initial validation of the conversational approach to research data discovery within the SOEP ecosystem.

2 Background and Related Work

The SOEP Dataset Landscape

The German Socio-Economic Panel, administered by the German Institute for Economic Research (DIW Berlin), represents one of the most comprehensive longitudinal studies in social science research. Since its inception in 1984, SOEP has collected annual data from thousands of households and individuals, creating a rich repository of information on income dynamics, employment patterns, education trajectories, health outcomes, and social attitudes (SOEP 2024, Goebel et al. 2019).

The dataset's complexity stems from its multi-dimensional structure: temporal (waves spanning nearly 40 years), cross-sectional (multiple subsamples including immigrants, high-income households, and refreshment samples), and topical (covering economics, sociology, psychology, and health domains). This complexity, while scientifically valuable, presents significant challenges for data users attempting to navigate and understand the available information (SOEP 2024, Wagner et al, 2007).

Historically, SOEP data access relies primarily on traditional methods: PDF documentation, static table based variable overviews on paneldata.org, and the SOEPcompanion (<https://companion.soep.de/>). While these resources are comprehensive, they often require substantial domain knowledge and can be time-consuming to navigate, particularly for researchers seeking specific variable information or attempting to understand how some variables or datasets relate to one another.

RAG Systems and Initial Experimentation

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is an approach that enhances large language models by combining them with external knowledge retrieval. Rather than relying only on the model's pre-trained knowledge, RAG systems *retrieve* relevant information from a knowledge base, then use this retrieved context to *augment* the model's context window (LLM's memory), thereby, significantly reducing hallucinations and improving factual accuracy (Gao et al. 2023, Shuster et al. 2021).

As part of the experimentation phase that led to this project, we initially explored a simple RAG architecture. This simple RAG implementation consisted of a small collection of text snippets describing a limited set of SOEP variables, stored in text format and indexed in a basic vector database. Queries were handled through straightforward similarity search, retrieving the most

semantically similar documents to augment the language model's responses. However, this approach quickly revealed significant scalability limitations. As the number of indexed documents and/or the data present in each document/chunk increased, the probability of retrieving irrelevant or incorrect context grew substantially. Simple similarity search proved insufficient for handling the complexity and scale of SOEP's comprehensive metadata. This limitation motivated our shift toward more sophisticated architectures incorporating agentic frameworks, dual-database systems that combine structured relational databases with vector stores, and row-level linkage between these components to maintain the relational metadata structure while enabling efficient semantic search.

3 System Design and Implementation

The system's architecture is designed to be modular and private, ensuring that sensitive research queries remain within a local environment. It is composed of a user interface, a dual-database knowledge base, an orchestration agent, and locally-run language models.

High-Level Architecture

The architecture comprises four main components: the user interface layer (OpenWebUI, <https://github.com/open-webui/open-webui>), the orchestration agent (Pydantic AI, <https://ai.pydantic.dev/>), the database (combining PostgreSQL, <https://postgresql.org>, and Qdrant, <https://qdrant.tech>), and the local open-weight large language models run via the Ollama (<https://ollama.com/>) framework.

OpenWebUI was selected as the frontend for its ChatGPT-like user experience (see Figure 1), customization options, and robust support for local model integration. It manages user authentication, conversation history, and model switching. The **Pydantic AI agent** acts as the central nervous system, orchestrating the flow of information between the user, the knowledge base, and the LLM. We employ a dual database approach: **PostgreSQL** stores structured metadata, ensuring relational integrity, while **Qdrant** serves as a high-performance vector database for semantic search. Finally, utilizing open-weight LLMs with **Ollama** ensures data privacy and eliminates dependency on external APIs.

DIW Assistant

Figure 1: OpenWebUI Interface.

Data Sourcing and Preparation

The metadata for the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) was sourced from two primary formats: a highly structured DDI-Codebook in XML format (Wenzig et al. 2025) and unstructured data from the SOEPcompanion, which contains a combination of textual and tabular information. Our data ingestion pipeline was built using Python to systematically parse these different sources. The decision to use the DDI-Codebook rather than SOEP's own metadata system directly was motivated by the intention to develop a reusable infrastructure that can be applied in other contexts beyond SOEP.

For the structured DDI-Codebook, we used the `xml.etree.ElementTree` library to precisely extract machine-readable elements like variable names and descriptive labels, alongside basic metadata for variables and datasets. For the unstructured data from the SOEP Companion, our process involved extracting both textual and tabular content, which was then processed using semantic chunking techniques (detailed in the next subsection). The SOEP Companion provided more comprehensive information about SOEP generally, including dataset editions, dataset structures, and variable naming conventions.

Following extraction, the metadata from both sources was cleaned and normalized to ensure consistency. Three datasets were created from this process: one structured dataset containing variable metadata, one structured dataset for dataset information, and one containing the semantically split chunks from the SOEP Companion data. These datasets were then prepared for the indexing phase of the RAG pipeline.

RAG Pipeline: Indexing Phase

The indexing phase is a one-time, offline process where the prepared source documents are transformed into a searchable knowledge base. This involves chunking, embedding, and storing the data.

For unstructured textual data, the ingested document objects were broken down into smaller, manageable chunks. We applied semantic chunking to ensure that the informational and contextual integrity of the source text is preserved within each chunk. In contrast to simple text splitting approaches that divide documents at predetermined intervals, semantic chunking identifies coherent segments based on content structure and meaning. For structured data, the relevant content of each row (e.g. variable label, dataset label) was treated as a separate chunk.

Next, each text chunk is converted into a high-dimensional vector representation using the (nomic-embed-text) model. This model was selected for its strong performance on semantic similarity tasks, its open-source license, and its relatively small size, which is suitable for a local deployment environment.

Finally, the resulting vector embeddings are stored in our dual-database system. Qdrant is used as the primary vector store for fast, approximate nearest-neighbor search, ideal for handling conceptual queries. In parallel, the raw text and structured metadata are stored in a PostgreSQL database, which serves as a ground-truth store for exact-match queries and maintains the relational links between variables, questions, and datasets.

RAG Pipeline: Retrieval and Generation Phase

The retrieval and generation phase occurs in real-time when a user submits a query. This multi-step process is orchestrated by the Pydantic AI agent to provide grounded, accurate answers.

1. **Query Analysis:** When a query is received via OpenWebUI, the Pydantic AI agent first uses a tool-calling LLM to analyze the user's intent. It determines whether the query is conceptual and requires semantic search or is specific and requires a direct database lookup. In production mode, however, the results of both query types may be integrated to provide a comprehensive response.
2. **Information Retrieval:** Based on the intent, the agent executes a retrieval action. For conceptual queries like "variables about life satisfaction," it queries Qdrant to find the most semantically similar document chunks. For precise queries like "What is the question for variable plh0188?", it executes a structured query against PostgreSQL to retrieve the exact entry. This is the core retrieval step.
3. **Context Augmentation:** The retrieved documents, variable descriptions, and metadata are then compiled and systematically injected into a new prompt along with the user's original query.
4. **Response Generation:** This augmented prompt is passed to a local language model (e.g., gpt-oss) running on Ollama. By using the retrieved context as its primary source of information, the LLM generates a coherent and factually grounded response, completing the generation step and minimizing the risk of hallucination.

This pipeline ensures that the LLM’s responses are not based on its internal, pre-trained knowledge but are directly grounded in the authoritative SOEP documentation, minimizing the risk of factual errors and hallucinations.

4 Evaluation and Preliminary Results

As a prototype, the system’s performance was evaluated through a series of qualitative tests and targeted queries designed to assess its ability to handle different types of information requests. The evaluation focused on three key criteria: relevance, accuracy, and coherence.

Qualitative Assessment

We crafted a series of representative queries that mimic a typical researcher's workflow. Figure 2 shows a small sample of those queries and their respective responses.

Query	Response																												
Are there any variables for mental health?	<p>Yes – the SOEP contains several variables that measure mental-health aspects. Below are a few of the most common ones, together with the dataset they belong to and a direct link to the variable description:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Variable</th> <th>Variable Label</th> <th>Dataset</th> <th>Link</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>mh_nbs</td> <td>Mental Health (NBS)</td> <td>health</td> <td>Link</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ill15</td> <td>Mental disorders</td> <td>bioagcl</td> <td>Link</td> </tr> <tr> <td>m11109</td> <td>Psychiatric problems</td> <td>pequiv</td> <td>Link</td> </tr> <tr> <td>jl1823</td> <td>Depression: Nervousness</td> <td>jugendl</td> <td>Link</td> </tr> <tr> <td>spcned4_fid</td> <td>Special needs: Mental</td> <td>bioagcl</td> <td>Link</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ple0192i02</td> <td>Reduced earning capacity: mental/emotional impairment</td> <td>pl</td> <td>Link</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>These variables can be used to assess various facets of mental health in the SOEP sample.</p>	Variable	Variable Label	Dataset	Link	mh_nbs	Mental Health (NBS)	health	Link	ill15	Mental disorders	bioagcl	Link	m11109	Psychiatric problems	pequiv	Link	jl1823	Depression: Nervousness	jugendl	Link	spcned4_fid	Special needs: Mental	bioagcl	Link	ple0192i02	Reduced earning capacity: mental/emotional impairment	pl	Link
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ple0192i02	Reduced earning capacity: mental/emotional impairment	pl	Link																										
Is there a dataset specifically for sample weightings?	<p>Yes – the SOEP provides dedicated weighting files:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Dataset</th> <th>Dataset Label</th> <th>Link</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>hhrf</td> <td>Household-level weighting and staying probabilities (sample weights for the household panel)</td> <td>Link</td> </tr> <tr> <td>phrf</td> <td>Person-level weighting and staying probabilities (sample weights for the individual panel)</td> <td>Link</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>These datasets contain the weighting variables you need to apply when estimating population-representative statistics.</p>	Dataset	Dataset Label	Link	hhrf	Household-level weighting and staying probabilities (sample weights for the household panel)	Link	phrf	Person-level weighting and staying probabilities (sample weights for the individual panel)	Link																			
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What does the variable 'hlf0445' measure?	<p>It records how many automobiles (cars) are owned by the household. hlf0445 – <i>Number of cars in the household</i> For more details about the variable, visit: Link</p>																												

Figure 2: Test Queries

The results from these tests were highly promising. The system consistently retrieved relevant and accurate information for both direct and conceptual queries. For instance, a search for “mental health” correctly retrieved variables related to depression and psychological distress, even if the exact term “mental health” was not present in the variable label. The responses generated were well-structured and coherent, providing clear explanations and citing the relevant variables, datasets and most importantly the corresponding links on paneldata.org.

Limitations of the Prototype

While the results are encouraging, the prototype has several key limitations. First, the system’s data coverage is not yet comprehensive; it currently indexes only a portion of the vast SOEP dataset. Queries related to un-indexed data will result in a “no information found in the retrieved context” response. Second, while the RAG approach significantly reduces hallucinations, the LLM may still occasionally misinterpret a user’s intent or fail to synthesize retrieved information perfectly, especially for highly complex, multi-step queries. Finally, the system does not yet have the capability to accurately generate code snippets (e.g., Stata or R code) for data manipulation, which would be a valuable feature for researchers.

5 Discussion and Future Work

This prototype demonstrates that a RAG system can provide a viable and powerful conversational interface for exploring complex research data. The ability to use natural language to navigate tens of thousands of variables represents a significant improvement over traditional, keyword-based search methods. However, the current implementation represents only an initial step toward a comprehensive conversational data discovery platform for SOEP.

Expanding Data Coverage

The most immediate priority is achieving complete coverage of all SOEP datasets and variables. As of December 2025, the system indexes only a subset of available data. Additionally, beyond the DDI-Codebook metadata and SOEP Companion, significant valuable information resides in unstructured PDF documentation, for example, methodological reports, survey design documents, and user guides. These documents contain contextual information about survey methodology, sampling strategies, and other relevant information that are crucial for informed data usage but difficult to capture in structured metadata alone.

Knowledge Representation

Another potential expansion is to use knowledge graphs for knowledge representation. The current vector-based retrieval system, while effective for semantic similarity matching, does not explicitly capture the rich relational structure inherent in panel data. Where variables are related through hierarchical taxonomies, temporal sequences, survey routing logic, and thematic connections. Representing these relationships explicitly through knowledge graphs could significantly enhance retrieval precision.

Expanding Agent Capabilities

The current system employs a single AI agent with a limited set of tools for database queries and vector search. Expanding the agent's toolkit could enable more sophisticated interactions. For example, tools both for statistical analysis and for code generation for Stata, R, or Python would help researchers transition smoothly from data discovery to data analysis. Multi-agent architectures present another avenue for enhancement. Specialized agents could handle distinct domains: a discovery agent for finding relevant variables, a methodology agent for explaining survey design and data collection procedures, alongside an analysis agent for suggesting appropriate analytical approaches. These agents could collaborate to address complex, multi-faceted queries that require integration of knowledge across different domains.

6 Conclusion

This paper presents a prototype RAG-based conversational interface for SOEP that demonstrates the feasibility of natural language interaction for research data discovery. By combining open-weight language models, vector similarity search, and structured metadata storage, the system enables researchers to explore SOEP's complex data landscape through intuitive conversations rather than manual documentation navigation. The prototype successfully retrieves relevant variables, datasets, and methodological information in response to both specific and conceptual queries, providing coherent, grounded responses that cite authoritative sources. The architecture's emphasis on local deployment ensures data privacy and eliminates dependence on external APIs, addressing key concerns for research institutions handling sensitive queries.

Although the current implementation covers only a portion of SOEP data and represents an early-stage prototype, it establishes a foundation for further comprehensive development. The path forward involves expanding data coverage, integrating graph-based knowledge representation, enhancing agent capabilities, and conducting rigorous evaluations with actual users. These enhancements will transform the prototype into a production-ready tool that meaningfully reduces barriers to SOEP data discovery. As research data continues to grow in complexity, conversational AI systems offer a promising approach to democratizing access and accelerating discovery. With continued refinement, such interfaces may become standard components of research data infrastructure, fundamentally transforming how researchers discover, understand, and utilize complex datasets.

Acknowledgments

This project has been funded by KonsortSWD.

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Imprint:

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<https://www.diw.de/de/soep>

December 2025

KonsortSWD Working Paper:

KonsortSWD, as part of the National Research Data Infrastructure, is expanding offerings to support research with data in the social, behavioural, educational, and economic sciences. Our mission is to strengthen, expand, and deepen the research data infrastructure for the study of society. It should be user-oriented and consider the needs of the research communities. An important cornerstone is the network of research data centres that has been built up for more than two decades by the German Data Forum (RatSWD).

This series contains articles on research data management that are produced in the context of KonsortSWD. Articles that have been externally and double-blind peer-reviewed are marked accordingly.

KonsortSWD is funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) within the framework of the NFDI – project number: 442494171.

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17643487](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17643487)

Citation suggestion:

Torossian, Paylag; Goebel, Jan and Wenzig, Knut (2025). *Chat about SOEP Research Data: A RAG System for Interactive SOEP Data Exploration*. KonsortSWD Working Paper 14/2025.

Konsortium für die Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs- und Wirtschaftswissenschaften (KonsortSWD). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17643487>